

Proposed Outlier Measure: The Anti-Beta Trimmed-Mean

Proposal to the Post 2000 Estimates Methods Committee
by the Outlier Subcommittee

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Summary

The Post 2000 Estimates Methods Committee (hereafter, the P2KEM Committee) tasked the Outlier Subcommittee to develop an outlier measure for evaluating the results of alternative methods of county population estimation. Given the accuracy measure chosen by the P2KEM Committee to evaluate the estimates, the Subcommittee proposes averaging the top five percent of the losses (hereafter, the “errors”) used to calculate accuracy as a measure of the “outlierhood” of a set of estimates. This measure is called the anti-beta trimmed-mean, with beta taken to be five percent. Among its useful properties, this measure has two major advantages. It is responsive to increasing errors. That is, as an error in the top fifth percentile increases, the outlier measure increases. It also has simplicity and is easily comprehended. A more complex measure may be difficult both to program and to explain to non-specialists, leading to loss of time and good will.

Overview

The P2KEM Committee decided that the most desirable (or “reasonable”) estimation procedure is one that minimizes apparent outliers. One interpretation of this preference is that the procedure should produce “reasonable” errors for entire distributions. Another interpretation is that it is not enough for a procedure to be more accurate overall; it should also not produce great inaccuracies for a small number of observations (i.e., areas). As shown below, the anti-beta trimmed-mean is not an attempt to detect or measure outliers per se, given that no null distribution of errors can be assumed. Rather, it measures the extreme values in sets of errors, permitting one to select as “most reasonable” the estimation procedure whose errors generate the smallest value on this measure.

Measure Considerations

1. Nonnegativity of Errors.

As noted above, the focus is on accuracy as opposed to bias. Both the absolute percentage error (APE) and Webster’s Rule work on absolute values. Thus, all errors discussed below are nonnegative.

2. Traditional Approaches to Detecting Outliers.

Traditional approaches to detecting outliers test one or more observations against a single assumed distribution for the population, or use measured outliers to find out whether the observations are being generated by more than one distribution.¹ However, for evaluating results of alternative county population estimation methods, we have no reason to believe that the errors in these results are generated by any single distribution. In fact, we believe that the errors are generated by multiple distributions of unknown forms.² Traditional methods cannot be used when there is no null distribution against which to test outliers.

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¹ Barnett and Lewis (1994) devote over 500 pages to the first type of problem.

² This view is taken by Coleman (1999).

3. Non-utility of Robust and Nonrobust Location Statistics.

Because a null distribution cannot be assumed, one cannot compare robust and nonrobust location statistics from a set of distributions (e.g., means and medians) to determine whether one distribution has appreciably more outliers than the other, due to random variation. Though this random variation can be accounted for by constructing test statistics, a null distribution has to be assumed.

4. Non-utility of Scale Measures Based on the Errors.

Scale measures also cannot be used, and for the same reason. Note that location statistics themselves are, in effect, scale measures.

5. Sensitivity to Severity of Outlier.

The chosen outlier measure must be appropriately sensitive to the severity of an outlier. An example demonstrates this lack when a scale measure is used. For this example, assume a quantile outlier measure, which chooses the third largest observation. When there are the following two sets of three-largest observations, (5,6,7) and (5,6,71), this outlier measure chooses “5” in both cases, so considers their underlying estimation procedures to be the “same” in error-proneness. However, it seems clear that they cannot be. The latter set of errors differs in its largest element by a factor greater than 10.

The Anti-Beta Trimmed-Mean

The anti-beta trimmed-mean, referred to as Obar, is simply the average of a chosen percentage of the largest errors, as used to calculate accuracy.³ Using the same distribution to determine both accuracy and outlierhood eases both programming and interpretation: the same inputs are used. Moreover, the calculation is simple.

Also, the anti-beta trimmed-mean reverses the logic of the beta trimmed-mean, a popular approach to ridding a distribution of the most extreme values. The beta trimmed-mean discards the β percentage of the largest errors, as it considers them to be potential outliers, and averages the rest.⁴ In contrast, Obar is sensitive to outlier severity: it averages the β percentage of the largest errors, as these are the most extreme observations. And the larger any extreme is, the larger Obar is. Using the two sets of largest observations from the earlier example and assuming them to be within the β percentage chosen, Obar’s value for each is 6 and 27, respectively, in contrast to “5” for both. Clearly, Obar results conform to our earlier opinion that the second set of errors is worse in terms of outlierhood.

Mathematically, Obar measures the (weighted) masses under the upper tails of observed distributions. The larger the measure, the further away a given mass is from zero. Obar thus can be used to compare methods. The method that generates the most extreme observations will have the largest Obar.

Choice of Beta

Beta has to be chosen both to assure a reasonable sample size and to prevent the incorporation of too many nonextreme observations. Theoretically, beta can vary between zero percent and one hundred percent. Setting beta too low results in capturing too few extreme observations, while setting beta too high results in capturing some ‘nonextreme’ observations and diluting effects of the most extreme ones. The Subcommittee believes that five percent is a reasonable value for β .

Conclusion

The Subcommittee recommends to the P2KEM Committee the anti-beta trimmed-mean as the measure of outlierhood. It is simple to calculate, easy to explain, and has an intuitive mathematical interpretation.

³ Obar is “O,” as in “Outlier,” and “bar,” as in “average.” It measures ‘extremeness.’

⁴ See Staudte and Sheather (1990, pp. 49,61) for one discussion of the beta trimmed-mean.

Disclaimer

This article was prepared, in part, by a U.S. Census Bureau employee as part of official duties. The U.S. Census Bureau bears no responsibility for its contents.

References

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